

IMPORTANT DIFFERENCES BETWEEN BRITISH AND AMERICAN ENGLISH AND USE IN PRACTICE

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Annotatsiya: Variations in grammar between the United Kingdom and the United States are significantly less significant than differences in vocabulary, functional language, gestures, and potentially even spelling and punctuation (all dealt with in separate articles on this site). However, pupils will undoubtedly encounter grammatical distinctions between US and UK English at some time, even if it is merely to be told that there was no need to correct themselves a minute ago or that both of the solutions given in the book are valid. This article summarizes the fundamental distinctions between grammar in American English and British English that students should be aware of, followed by teaching recommendations and classroom activities for presenting and practicing those differences.

Kalit soʻzlar: Grammar, language learning, grammatical distinctions, American English, British English, functional language.

INTRODUCTION

Learning English is challenging since there are many grammatical and spelling discrepancies between English spoken around the world. The most notable examples are British and American English grammar. Many terms have different pronunciations and meanings as well. While you might believe that learning English would be simple, it is not; after all, how different can English be from English? There are a few other aspects to consider: Canadian, Australian, South African, Indian English, and so on. These variances must be considered while studying the English language. Despite the growing relevance of other types of English, the contrasts between British and American English continue to captivate and perplex my students. The majority of the arts and media they consume (newspapers, movies, TV shows, etc.) are also in one of those two types of English. Furthermore, Canadian and Australian English contain a mix of British and American forms, so practicing UK and US English can aid if those other varieties arise later. As a result, I like to address UK and US English at every level, and I frequently conduct a longer segment or even a whole lecture on the subject. Despite many cross-cultural influences, it appears that the vocabularies, spellings, and pronunciations of these diverse dialects of English are diverging more and more with each passing year. It is critical to be understood correctly in order to be consistent in the use of spoken or written English. A non-native speaker must

understand whether terms are distinct and/or have distinct meanings and pronunciations depending on whether they are taught by a British or an American teacher. This is critical for effective communication and avoiding undue humiliation and misunderstandings.

Where there are variances in spelling between British and American English, American English is often more letter-efficient. The phonetic spelling in American English is brief. Unneeded letters are omitted, and most words are spelt how they sound. For example, in American English, the letter u is omitted in terms like color, flavor, neighbor, humor, honor, and so on. We can contrast the words traveling, jewelry, and program in American English with their equivalents in British English. This rule, however, does not always apply; for example, honorary, honorific, monorail, and honorarium are spelled the same on both sides.

Regional variants in pronunciation exist within both countries (as well as other countries, as previously indicated), however the following is a short list of some of the words that are commonly pronounced differently by the British and the Americans. The main distinction is made by employing various vowel sounds or different stress words inside a sentence. The following table words are stressed differently in the two dialects:

- ballet-BrE, ballet-AmE
- address - BrE, address – AmE
- garage - BrE, garage – AmE
- advertisement - BrE, advertisement – AmE

The pronunciations of some common words are very different in both variations of English.

- vase: vars as in cars (BrE), vace as in face (AmE)
- route: root as in shoot (BrE), rout as in shout (AmE)
- buoy: boy as in toy (BrE), boeuy as in the French name Louis (AmE)
- ate: etas inlet (BrE), ate as in late (AmE)

Only one or two countries use a small percentage of the total English vocabulary. The problem for English students and learners is that these are some of the most common and extensively used words in the language. Many words used solely by Americans are understood by the British, and vice versa. However, there are a few that can be difficult for novice students. Most British people know that fries are chips, chips are crisps, a vacation is a holiday, biscuits are cookies, flats are apartments, and a movie is a movie, but not everyone knows what an alumna or a fender is. Most Americans know that what they call a yard is called a garden, and trucks are called lorries, but common British English words like aubergine, plimsolls, barney or oflicence will mean nothing at all to American.

The bulk of words in British and American English grammar are identical. However, there are numerous minor and intriguing variations. Some verb forms, for example, differ from one another. Fit is the past tense in American English; fitted is the past tense in British English. Americans would say I've come to know her well; the British would say I've had a chance to get to know her well. The present perfect tense is usually employed in British English for circumstances where the past simple tense would be used in American English.

When it comes to teaching American and British English with differences and similarities comes with, it is another thing to ponder about. For example, when we are teaching Present Perfect, I tend to follow the textbook and my own speech in teaching “have + PP” with “yet” and “already”. However, I briefly tell students that Americans use Past Simple with those words and so students don't need to worry about which they use. I then accept both forms in all written and spoken practice. I have the same process for most points above, namely:

- Decide which form is preferable for that class of students
- Teach that form,
- Maybe briefly mention the other form
- Accept the other form

To decide which form above to present, you should consider:

- Which is in the textbook/ on the syllabus
- Which students will have studied before
- Which students will come across more in arts and media such as newspapers and TV series
- Which is or is becoming more internationally standard
- If these students will benefit more from practising something that they already know or will benefit more from learning something new

There are a few circumstances in which I would teach an entire session on the distinctions between British and American grammar, for example:

- If there have been a lot of queries about UK and US grammar in the last few classes
- If pupils are mostly familiar with one form but will need to adjust to the other, for example
- If they have primarily studied US English but will be attending a British university

Before or after studying more significant differences Variances between the United Kingdom and the United States include differences in terminology. Giving students an original text and a version that has been rewritten in the other form to spot the differences between is probably the easiest way to present

grammatical differences in such classes. There are a few circumstances in which I would teach an entire class about British and American grammatical differences, such as in (without showing their pages to each other). This can also be utilized as a practice exercise, and some of the following practice activities could also be used during the presentation stage.

The role of practicing regularly has a vital role to play to progress and learn differences gradually. Give one student a worksheet with British grammatical phrases like "I've already finished it" and "fill in this form," and the other student a worksheet with American grammar phrases like "I've already finished it", "fill out this form", and so on. Students compete to use as many of their phrases as possible during a role-play interaction between a British and an American, such as a business meeting or tourist information. Students that are more creative may strive to employ appropriate terminology, pronunciation, cultural references, and so on. You can then assess their recall of which grammar was on which worksheet.

CONCLUSION

This article summarizes the key differences in grammar that students should be aware of in American English and British English, followed by teaching recommendations and classroom activities for presenting and practicing those differences and similarities.

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